

ABOUT SPEAKER

Welcome to the world of Dr. Prashant Raghav

Dr. Prashant Raghav is a dedicated and highly motivated researcher and educator with a strong background in pharmacology. He possesses a diverse skill set, a commitment to learning and research, and the ability to work effectively in multidisciplinary settings. Dr. Raghav's academic journey includes a Ph.D. in Pharmaceutical Sciences, a Master's in Pharmacology, and a Bachelor's in Pharmacy. He has extensive teaching experience and has taught a variety of pharmacy-related subjects.

In addition to his academic roles, Dr. Raghav has practical experience in the pharmaceutical industry and currently serves as a principal. He has made significant contributions to the field, with presentations at international and national conferences on topics like hypo-glycemic and antidiabetic activity and analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties of certain compounds. He actively participates in seminars, conferences, and workshops to stay updated in his field and has engaged in collaborative research with industry partners.

Dr. Prashant Raghav's remarkable career is marked by his dedication to research, open-mindedness, and diverse skill set, making him a respected figure in the field of pharmacology and education.

Dr. Prashant Raghav

NATIONAL CONFERENCE ON RECENT ADVANCES IN DRUG DISCOVERY AND DEVELOPMENT

(RFDDD- 2023)

VISIT US: www.researcherforce.com

Registration: INR 499
December 17, 2023 (Sunday)

RESEARCHER FORCE

ABOUT RESEARCHER FORCE

Welcome to The Researcher Force, a trailblazing collective of visionary researchers dedicated to reshaping the landscape of multidisciplinary innovation. Our mission is simple yet profound: to harness the power of collaboration and bring together exceptional minds from diverse fields under one ambitious banner.

The Pinnacle of Expertise

At The Researcher Force, we boast a team of preeminent researchers whose dedication to advancing knowledge knows no bounds. With unrivalled proficiency in their specialized domains, our researchers have authored an impressive array of over 100+ review and research papers. These publications have graced the pages of prestigious journals, including Scopus, Elsevier, SCI, NCBI, PubMed, and NLM Indexed Journals.

Driving Innovation, Claiming Patents

Our founders, luminaries in their respective spheres, hold a collective portfolio of more than 13 patents. These patents stand as a testament to our relentless pursuit of innovation and our unwavering commitment to pushing the boundaries of what is possible.

Breaking Barriers, Forging Progress

The Researcher Force is an entity that transcends traditional disciplinary boundaries. Our ethos is rooted in a shared passion for advancing the frontiers of science and engineering positive change across all domains.

Join Our Vanguard

Whether you are an accomplished researcher seeking new horizons for collaboration or a burgeoning scientist yearning for mentorship and growth, The Researcher Force beckons you. We firmly believe that innovation flourishes in an environment of diversity and collaboration, and together, we have the power to redefine the very limits of human knowledge.

Embrace the opportunity to join us on this extraordinary journey of exploration, invention, and transformation. Together, we form The Researcher Force—an unstoppable force forging a brighter, more enlightened future for all

NATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON
**RECENT ADVANCES IN DRUG
DISCOVERY AND DEVELOPMENT**

CHAIR PERSON

DR. PRASHANT RAGHAV

DIRECTOR, DSRM COLLEGE OF PHARMACY, THAKURDWARA, MORADABAD

SUNDAY | DECEMBER 17 | 02.00 -03.00 PM

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